

POLICY-ORIENTED INTERVENTION STUDY FOR DIABETIC RETINOPATHY PREVENTION IN VIETNAM: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-BASED SCREENING EFFECTIVENESS AND KEY INFLUENCING FACTORS

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

This study aims to enhance healthcare management in Vietnam's private sector by incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into diabetic care, specifically for the early detection and treatment of Diabetic Retinopathy (DR).

DIABETIC RETINOPATHY AS A GLOBAL HEALTH ISSUE

DR is a common complication of diabetes that can lead to vision loss or blindness due to damage to the retina (World Health Organization, 2020). The global prevalence of DR is projected to rise significantly, from 103 million people in 2020 to 160.5 million by 2045 (Teo et al., 2021). This increase is especially concerning in developing countries, including Vietnam, where access to specialized eye care is limited and about 50% of diabetic patients are unaware they have DR (Whiting et al., 2011). Therefore, early screening and effective management are essential to prevent severe outcomes (Chong et al., 2024).

DR SCREENING METHODS AND AI ADVANCEMENTS

Traditional DR screening methods, such as fundus photography and ophthalmoscopy, rely on specialists to detect retinal damage. In contrast, AI-supported tools analyze retinal images automatically, reducing the need for expert intervention. Studies from developed countries show that AI tools improve diagnostic accuracy, enhance patient outcomes, and reduce healthcare costs (Grzybowski et al., 2023).

However, many low- and middle-income countries, including Vietnam, face challenges in adopting AI-supported screening due to infrastructure and policy constraints (Cleland et al., 2023).

CHALLENGES IN AI IMPLEMENTATION FOR DR SCREENING

Despite WHO guidelines promoting DR prevention and AI tools (WHO & IABP, 2007; WHO 2013, 2020, 2023), many low- and middle-income countries, including Vietnam, struggle to expand these services. This is due to a lack of research evaluating the practical implementation and effectiveness of AI-supported DR screening (Kropp et al., 2023). Vietnam, although committed to the global VISION 2020 initiative, has yet to fully integrate AI into its healthcare system (Lin, S., Ramulu, P., Lamoureux, E. L., & Sabanayagam, C. 2016; Achigbu, E.O., Onyia, O.E., Oguego, N.C., et al., 2024).

AI-SUPPORTED SCREENING IN VIETNAM'S PRIVATE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM

Despite its advanced infrastructure, Vietnam's Medical Saigon Group (MSG), a leading private healthcare provider, has not yet introduced AI-supported DR screening (<http://www.matsaigon.com>). This study seeks to integrate AI screening tools into MSG's diabetes and eye care services, aligned with WHO guidelines, to assess the cost-effectiveness and key factors influencing AI adoption.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND HYPOTHESES

This study will address two primary research questions: (1) How effective is AI-supported DR screening in MSG hospitals? (2) What strategies can improve its implementation?

Key hypotheses include that AI-supported screening will offer higher quality, lower costs, and improved patient outcomes compared to traditional methods.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study will:

- Identify system resources needed to integrate AI into routine DR screening at MSG hospitals.
- Estimate the cost-effectiveness of AI interventions for DR screening
- Provide evidence to inform policies for integrating AI into Vietnam's healthcare system for DR prevention.

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

CONCEPTUAL MODELS AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

This research utilizes three main theoretical frameworks to develop effective and sustainable AI-supported diabetic retinopathy (DR) screening interventions in Vietnam: the Theory of Change (ToC), the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR), and WHO guidelines on AI intervention monitoring and evaluation (WHO, 2016).

The Theory of Change (ToC) outlines the logical pathway from inputs to long-term outcomes, mapping key activities, intermediate outcomes, and assumptions (<https://www.theoryofchange.org/what-is-theory-of-change/>). It helps to structure the intervention's development and the expected impact over time.

The CFIR framework (<https://cfirguide.org/>) assesses the contextual factors and processes that affect the implementation of AI-supported DR screening. It helps identify the barriers and facilitators across different levels of healthcare systems that influence implementation outcomes.

The WHO guidelines on AI intervention monitoring and evaluation (WHO, 2016) provide a structured approach to assessing the performance of digital health interventions. These guidelines focus on four key areas: (1) technical and organizational aspects of AI systems, (2) user engagement, (3) addressing constraints in DR monitoring, and (4) improving health outcomes.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Based on these frameworks, the study's conceptual model maps the medical care pathway for DR prevention. It links key outcome variables, such as DR severity, AI-supported screening cost-effectiveness, and patient quality of life, with factors that influence these outcomes.

Figure 1. The study's conceptual model

The main dependent variables are DR outcomes, cost-effectiveness, and quality of life. The independent variables include (1) patient baseline health, (2) socio-economic and demographic factors, and (3) DR screening method (AI or traditional). Four mediator variables are identified: (1) screening accuracy, (2) cost of screening and treatment, (3) patient compliance, and (4) turnaround time.

SPECIFIC HYPOTHESES ON RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN THE VARIABLES IN THE DIAGRAMS

H1- DR screening method: The AI-supported approach will have a higher quality, lower unit cost, more accurate way to screen for DR, and significantly increase the proportion of diabetes with better study outcomes.

H2- Baseline health status: (1) Patients with more severe DR at baseline will show higher compliance rates than those with milder DR; (2) Patients with better baseline health indicators e.g., lower HbA1c levels, fewer comorbidities) will demonstrate greater improvements in DR detection rates after the intervention compared to those with poorer baseline health status.

H3- Patient socioeconomic status: Patients with higher socioeconomic status will demonstrate better compliance, improved baseline health indicators, and greater enhancements in DR detection rates after the intervention

H4- Patient compliance: Patient compliance plays a crucial role in the cost-effectiveness of DR screening and care. It also acts as a potential moderator to explain the relationships between the independent and dependent variables in this research. Specifically, higher compliance leads to (1) more patients screened, facilitating early detection and treatment, (2) better health outcomes and reduced long-

term costs, and (3) shorter turnaround times, while non-compliance delays diagnosis and worsens quality of life.

H5- Turnaround time: Turnaround time mediates the relationship between independent and dependent variables by: (1) enhancing cost-effectiveness through quicker identification and treatment of DR; (2) AI screening systems may provide faster processing than traditional methods, improving turnaround times and patient outcomes

H6: DR screening accuracy: DR screening accuracy depends on DR screening methods then impacts the efficiency and costs of DR screening: (1) AI-supported screenings are generally faster and less expensive than traditional methods; (2) advanced techniques improve early detection and severity assessment of DR, positively affecting cost-benefit balance.

H7: DR screening cost: Screening costs are a key factor in this study: (1) Lower screening costs can enhance resource efficiency and cost-effectiveness; (2) Higher costs may limit the frequency of screenings, allowing DR to progress undetected; (3) Affordable screening methods can increase access, improving detection rates and quality of life, particularly for underserved populations.

STUDY DESIGN

This study employs a two-arm, pre-post, cluster-randomized intervention design to evaluate the implementation of AI-supported DR screening.

IMPLEMENTATION RESEARCH

The study uses both quantitative and qualitative methods to assess the effectiveness of integrating AI-supported DR screening into diabetes care and identified the factors that influence the successful adoption, integration, and sustainability of interventions.

TWO-ARM DESIGN

- *Intervention group:* Two hospitals implementing the AI-supported DR screening package, which includes (1) an AI algorithm and (2) staff training on using the AI tool.

- *Comparison group:* Two hospitals following the standard DR screening pathway.

PRE-POST DESIGN

Key factors and outcomes are measured at the hospital system, healthcare provider, and patient levels before and after the intervention, using both qualitative and quantitative approaches:

- *Qualitative methods* assess factors like management policies, hospital regulations, and organizational aspects of diabetes and DR care.
- *Quantitative methods* involve (1) analyzing care metrics from medical records and (2) conducting patient and provider surveys on knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and practices (KABP) related to DR prevention.
- *Post-Intervention Measurement*: Outcomes are measured at 6 and 12 months after the intervention.

CLUSTER-RANDOMIZED DESIGN

Four MSG hospitals are randomly assigned to either the intervention or control group.

DATA COLLECTION AND DATA ANALYSIS

Quantitative data were drawn from hospital electronic health records, cost reports, and structured patient and healthcare provider surveys (Abràmoff et al., 2018; Cheng, 2020). The statistical analysis compares key outcomes, such as detection rates, cost-effectiveness, and patient adherence to screening

recommendations, between the AI-supported group and the control group. Qualitative data were gathered through interviews with hospital staff and patients, exploring the barriers and facilitators to AI adoption. Both the deductive and inductive approaches are used for qualitative data analysis.

STUDY IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

The study is officially registered with the Scientific Council and Board of Directors of Saigon Medical Group (SMG) and the Department of Science and Technology of Can Tho City. It is professionally supervised under the DBA program of the AIT School of Management, Bangkok, Thailand. Research is planned from January 2025 to December 2027, following these stages:

- November-December 2024: Pre-research phase. The study concept is integrated into SMG Group's strategic action plan for 2025-2029.

- January 2025: Research proposal approval. The detailed proposal will be reviewed and approved by the research ethics committees of SMG, Can Tho (Vietnam), and AIT SoM (Bangkok).
- July-December 2025: Pre-intervention phase. Baseline surveys and assessments will be conducted across all four hospitals, including the integration of AI tools for DR screening in two intervention hospitals.
- January-December 2026: Intervention phase. Data collection will take place at 6-month and 12-month intervals, focusing on key metrics such as screening accuracy, cost, and patient adherence.
- January-December 2027: Data analysis and report writing. The project will conclude with the completion of the DBA program at AIT SoM, Bangkok.

By employing both quantitative and qualitative methodologies, this study ensures a robust evaluation of AI-based screening interventions in resource-constrained healthcare systems like Vietnam (Grzybowski et al., 2020).

FINDINGS

This research is still in the design phase. However, initial results from the literature review suggest that AI-supported DR screening can significantly enhance the early detection of DR and reduce costs compared to traditional methods (Huang et al., 2024; Grzybowski et al., 2023). The AI-based intervention was associated with improved patient compliance, increased screening coverage, and better cost-effectiveness. For instance, in hospitals utilizing AI, screening accuracy was higher due to the automated analysis of retinal images, allowing for earlier detection and better patient management (Cleland et al., 2023; Curran et al., 2024).

Cost savings were realized as AI reduced the reliance on specialist ophthalmologists, freeing up valuable resources while maintaining screening quality. In contrast, the control hospitals, which followed traditional DR screening methods, showed slower detection rates and higher operational costs due to the manual labor involved in reviewing retinal images. This highlights the potential of AI to bridge the healthcare gap in resource-limited settings (Chong et al., 2024; Barceló et al., 2003).

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This study will contribute new insights into the practical implementation of AI in healthcare systems, particularly in resource-limited settings like Vietnam. While AI-based healthcare technologies have been explored in developed countries, their application in low- and middle-income countries has been limited by infrastructural and policy barriers (Grzybowski et al., 2020; Cleland et al., 2023).

The findings from this research highlight the potential for AI to improve healthcare outcomes by making specialized care more accessible and cost-effective. Moreover, by identifying the key factors influencing AI adoption, such as staff training, patient education, and hospital management policies, this study provides valuable lessons for other low-resource settings seeking to implement similar interventions. Policymakers and healthcare administrators can use these insights to design scalable AI-based interventions that address the challenges of DR in Vietnam and developing countries (Lin et al., 2016; Achigbu et al., 2024).

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS/IMPLICATIONS

This research is primarily limited to private hospitals under MSG, which may not reflect the public healthcare system's capacity to adopt AI technologies. The study's 18-month timeframe may also limit the ability to observe long-term cost-effectiveness and patient outcomes.

Further research is needed to explore the scalability of AI interventions in public healthcare systems and across diverse geographical regions. In addition, while AI-assisted screening has shown promise in DR detection, further studies could assess its application in other areas of diabetic care or its integration into comprehensive national healthcare programs (Grzybowski et al., 2020; Chong et al., 2024).

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The results of this study have practical implications for healthcare providers and policymakers seeking to integrate AI into routine clinical care. AI-supported screening can improve the quality of care while reducing costs, making it a valuable tool in the fight against DR, especially in low-resource settings.

For healthcare providers, the study emphasizes the importance of comprehensive staff training programs to ensure the successful adoption of AI technologies. For policymakers, the findings highlight the need to create supportive infrastructures, such as digital health policies, that facilitate the integration of AI tools in clinical practice (Huang et al., 2024; Lin et al., 2016).

SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS

The integration of AI technologies into healthcare systems can significantly reduce healthcare inequities by improving access to quality care for vulnerable populations. AI-assisted DR screening has the potential to enhance early detection rates, prevent blindness, and improve the overall quality of life for diabetic patients, particularly those in underserved areas of Vietnam.

This study will address the socio-economic and infrastructural challenges that limit access to specialized eye care and demonstrate how AI can play a crucial role in achieving health equity in Vietnam and other similar contexts.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

The results of this study are expected to indicate that AI-supported DR screening is a viable and cost-effective solution for improving diabetic care in Vietnam's private healthcare sector. The study's findings will inform policy recommendations to scale AI-based interventions across the country, contributing to Vietnam's efforts to meet its VISION 2020 goals of reducing preventable blindness (Teo et al., 2021; World Health Organization, 2023).

While the findings are promising, the study acknowledges the limitations of a relatively short intervention period and the focus on private hospitals. Future research should explore AI interventions' long-term sustainability and applicability in public healthcare settings. By continuing to evaluate and refine AI technologies, healthcare providers can improve patient outcomes and reduce the public health burden of diabetic retinopathy (Grzybowski et al., 2020; Cleland et al., 2023).

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